

Molecular Phylogenetic Prevalence of *Entamoeba gingivalis* in Oral Mucosa of Dental Patients and Association to Risk Factors in Wasit Province, Iraq

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Abstract

Background: *Entamoeba gingivalis* is a protozoan parasite which commonly found in the oral cavity of humans due to the poor oral hygiene prompting investigation into its possible role in periodontal pathology. **Aim:** Indicate the molecular incidence of *E. gingivalis* in oral lesions of individuals in Wasit province (Iraq), sequencing and phylogenetic analysis of positive study *E. gingivalis* isolates, and investigate the association of positivity to some related-sociodemographic risk factors. **Materials and methods:** An overall 137 individuals of various oral lesions attended to some private dentistry clinics in Wasit province (Iraq) during April (2025) were subjected to sampling of saliva and dental swabs. Conventional PCR assay was utilized to indicate the positive samples that then sent for sequencing as well as phylogenetic analysis by the MEGA-11 Software. Sociodemographic data were obtained from the study population and applied to estimate the incidence and risk of infection among the groups of each studied factor. **Results:** molecular PCR revealed that the incidence rate of *E. gingivalis* infection in saliva and/or oral lesions was 10.95%. Targeting the *SrRNA* gene, phylogenetic analysis of study and NCBI-BLAST *E. gingivalis* isolates / strains detected that 14 of study isolates (PX369135.1 to PX369148.1) were identical to NCBI-BLAST Japanese *E. gingivalis* isolate (LC832203.1) while one study isolate (PX369149.1) has an identity to NCBI-BLAST Mexican *E. gingivalis* strain (KX027296.1). Regarding the sociodemographic data, positive *E. gingivalis* infections were distributed differently throughout the factors of health status, age, smoking, and sex but not for other factors including residence, marital status, and pregnancy status. However, the risk of infection was increased significantly in dental patients, 36-50 years age old, urban population, smokers, married individuals, females, and pregnant women. **Conclusion:** This represents the first molecular phylogenetic study in Wasit province suggesting that furthermore researches are necessary to investigate the incidence rate of *E. gingivalis* in various categories of human populations and the strains that circulate in different regions.

Keywords: Conventional polymerase chain reaction (PCR), Oral parasites, Periodontal diseases, Sequencing data, Sociodemographic factors.

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Introduction

The oral cavity has the second largest number and variety of microorganisms in the body, housing millions of these organisms in the form of oral microbiota that having the ability to forming the biofilms and coexists in the symbiotic harmony with the host (Mosaddad et al., 2019; de Barros Santos et al.,

2025). However, when the microbial equilibrium is broken, different oral diseases such as dental caries and periodontal disease can occur (Nyvad and Takahashi, 2020). In oral cavity of healthy individuals, although bacteria are the most abundant microorganisms, some studies investigate the colonization the oral cavity of both healthy individuals and those with periodontal disease, yielding variable results (Kitamoto et al., 2020; Puzio et al., 2021; Selahbarzin et al., 2024).

Entamoeba gingivalis is an opportunistic amoeboid parasite that first detected by Gross in 1849 from human tooth tartar, making it the first parasitic amoeba reported in humans, though it was initially suspected to be nonpathogenic (Oladokun et al., 2021). Taxonomy of the parasite classifies it in the Archamoebae class, under the Amoebozoa phylum that belongs to the kingdom of Protista (Schaap and Schilde, 2018; Samba-Louaka et al., 2019). *Entamoeba gingivalis* exhibits a direct life cycle characterized by trophozoite replication within the gingival crevice and occasional encystation in response to unfavorable environmental conditions (Bao et al., 2020). The encysted forms increase resistance to desiccation and antimicrobial agents, enabling persistence in the oral niche until favorable conditions trigger excystation and renewed trophozoite proliferation (Bonner et al., 2018). In addition, direct transmission of trophozoites to new host would imply that they are resistant to oxygen, which raises questions about how *E. gingivalis* is transmitted in nature, and what ecological niche services as reservoir (Bonner et al., 2018; Bao et al., 2020). However, transmission might chiefly spread through direct oral contact such as saliva exchange, sharing of eating utensils, and using of contaminated dental instruments, enabling rapid dissemination within close-contact populations (Ryabokon et al., 2020). Asymptomatic colonization of the parasite repeatedly detected in oral cavity can therefore serve as a reservoir, underscoring the importance of routine screening and hygiene interventions to curb protozoan spread (Puzio et al., 2021; Ghazy et al., 2025). Traditionally, diagnosis of *E. gingivalis* infection is made by microscopic examination of tooth and gum scraping stained with routine microbiologist stains, or rarely tissue biopsies stained with hematoxylin and eosin, periodic acid-Schiff, and Masson's trichrome (Bao, 2020). Unlike the other human infecting *Entamoeba* species, *E. gingivalis* exists only in the trophozoite stage, without cyst stage, as round to oval irregular shape with single nucleus and pseudopod projections while the cytoplasm is finely granular and may contain ingested bacteria, epithelial cells, leukocytes and erythrocytes (Garcia, 2008; Bonner et al., 2014; Mark Bonner, 2022). In last decades, molecular assays offer advantages over traditional methods by providing superior sensitivity and specificity, enabling the accurate identification of morphologically similar parasites and the detection of parasites even when they are present in low numbers. These tests also provide reliable, less subjective results that are unaffected by environmental factors and can utilized crucially for epidemiological studies to track disease outbreaks and study genetic variations (Tavares et al., 2011; Bradbury et al., 2022; Aththanayaka et al., 2024).

In Iraq, the number of studies investigated conventionally (Abbass et al., 2020; Al-Muathen et al., 2020; Al-Nuaimi et al., 2021; Shayal and ALAboody, 2025) and molecularly (Al-Nuaimi et al., 2021; Al-Sarhan et al., 2021; Mushtaq and Al-Abboodi, 2024) the incidence of *E. gingivalis* remains few with very limited sequencing data obtained from the patients in Babylon (Al-Jubory and Al-Hamairy, 2021), Nineveh (Al-Nuaimi et al., 2021), and Thi-Qar (Shayal and ALAboody, 2025) provinces; while in Wasit province, only one conventional study has been conducted by Naeem (2024) with surprising lack of molecular and/or sequencing investigations. Therefore, this study aims to firstly indicate the molecular incidence of *E. gingivalis* in individuals attended to some private dentistry clinics in Wasit province (Iraq), sequencing and phylogenetic analysis of positive study *E. gingivalis* isolates, and investigate the association of positivity to some related-risk factors to estimate the incidence and risk of infection among the various groups of each factor.

Materials and Methods

Samples and Data

Overall 137 individuals who attended to some private dentistry clinics in Wasit province (Iraq) during April (2025) with various oral lesions were selected randomly to the present study. Under aseptic conditions, oral swab samples were collected from each study individual (saliva and/or dental lesions), and transferred into one plastic tube to be considered as one sample. All obtained samples were transported cooled and saved frozen at -20°C until be examined molecularly.

Different sociodemographic data were collected from the study population compromising health status (healthy, patient), age (<20, 20-35, 36-50, >50 years), sex (female, male), residence (rural, sub-urban, urban), smoking (smoker, non-smoker), marital status (married, not-married), and pregnancy status (pregnant, not-pregnant).

Molecular Examination

After preparation of oral swabs at room temperature, DNAs were extracted following the manufacturer instruction of gSYNC™ DNA extraction kit (Genaid, Taiwan) and examined by the Nandrop spectrophotometer. For preparing the MasterMix tubes at a final volume of 25µl,

AccuPower® PCR PreMix Kit (Bioneer, Korea) and one set of primers (BarF: 5'-AAA CTG CGG ACG GCT CAT TA-3' and BarR: 5'-TCC ACC AAC TAA GAA CGG CC-3') which designated based on NCBI-GenBank *E. gingivalis* isolates (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/nucleotide/D28490.1>) were utilized. Post amplification in Thermal Cycler system at the modified conditions (Table 1), electrophoresis of PCR products was performed in 1% agarose-gel for 90 minutes at 80 Am and 100 Volt and the positive samples for *E. gingivalis* isolates were visualized throughout the UV illuminator at an approximately product size of 1212 bp.

Table 1. Thermal Cycler Conditions for Conventional PCR Reaction

Step	Temperature / Time	Cycle No.
Initial denaturation	95°C / 5 min.	1
Denaturation	95°C / 30 sec.	35
Annealing	57°C / 30 sec.	
Extension	72°C / 1 min.	
Final extension	72°C / 5 min.	1

Sequencing and Phylogeny

The DNAs of all positive *E. gingivalis* isolates were sequenced by the Macrogen Company (Korea), and the received data were submitted in the NCBI-GenBank database, and got specific access numbers. Then the sequence data were analysed phylogenetically by the MEGA software (*version 11*) and the NCBI-Viewer (*version 1.26*) throughout the multiple sequence alignment, homology sequence identity, and phylogenetic tree analysis to indicate the close-relationship between the study local and NCBI-BLAST *E. gingivalis* isolates / strains.

Statistical Analysis

The *t*-test and one-way ANOVA in the GraphPad Prism Software in addition to Odds Ratio (OR) and Relative Risk (RR) in the MedCalc Software were utilized to identify variation in incidence of positive infection among groups of sociodemographic factors and the risk of *E. gingivalis* infection. Differences were considered significant at $p < 0.0001$ (***), $p < 0.001$ (**), $p < 0.01$ (*), and $p < 0.05$ (*); whereas values were represented in the current study as either number (percentage) [No. (%)] or mean \pm standard error (M \pm SE), (Ajaj et al., 2021; Gharban et al., 2024).

Results

Molecular Findings

Targeting the *SrRNA* gene, the incidence rate of *E. gingivalis* infection in totally 137 individuals attended to some private dentistry clinics in Wasit province (Iraq) was 15 (10.95%); whereas, 122 (89.05%) individuals were shown a negative results for *E. gingivalis* infection (Figures 1, 2).

Figure 1. Total Results of Molecular PCR Assay among 137 Study Individuals

Figure 2. Electrophoresis of Some Positive PCR Products for *E. gingivalis* in 1% Agarose-Gel

Sequencing and Phylogeny

The sequencing data of all study positive *E. gingivalis* isolates (total number = 15) were submitted in the NCBI-GenBank database under specific names (Iraq-Hasbraa1 to Iraq-Hasbraa15) and subsequently under specific access numbers (PX369136.1 to PX369149.1, respectively). Then, phylogenetic analysis of study and NCBI-BLAST *E. gingivalis* isolates / strains detected the presence of similarity (*) at range of 99.03-99.82% and mutations / changes at range of 0.001-0.02%. However, multiple sequence alignment, homology sequence identity, and phylogenetic tree analysis detected that 14 of study *E. gingivalis* isolates (PX369135.1 to PX369148.1) were identical to NCBI-BLAST Japanese *E. gingivalis* isolate (LC832203.1) that identified in saliva; while, one study *E. gingivalis* isolate (PX369149.1) was having an identity to NCBI-BLAST Mexican *E. gingivalis* strain (KX027296.1) that isolated from periodontal scraping from oral cavity (Table 2, Figures 3-5).

Table 2. Homology Sequence Identity (%) of the Current Study *E. gingivalis* Isolates and Global NCBI-GenBank *E. gingivalis* Isolates / Strains

Local isolate		NCBI-BLAST isolate			Identity (%)
Name	Access. No.	Source	Country	Access. No.	
Iraq-Hasbraa1	PX369135.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.83

Iraq- Hasbraa2	PX369136.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.75
Iraq-Hasbraa3	PX369137.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.81
Iraq-Hasbraa4	PX369138.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.71
Iraq-Hasbraa5	PX369139.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.71
Iraq-Hasbraa6	PX369140.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.69
Iraq-Hasbraa7	PX369141.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.65
Iraq-Hasbraa8	PX369142.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.65
Iraq-Hasbraa9	PX369143.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.65
Iraq-Hasbraa10	PX369144.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.44
Iraq-Hasbraa11	PX369145.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.38
Iraq-Hasbraa12	PX369146.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.27
Iraq-Hasbraa13	PX369147.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.14
Iraq-Hasbraa14	PX369148.1	Saliva / Human	Japan	LC832203.1	99.03
Iraq-Hasbraa15	PX369149.1	Periodontal scraping / Human	Mexico	KX027296.1	99.82

Figure 3. Multiple Sequence Alignment for the Current Study and Global NCBI-BLAST *E. gingivalis* Isolates/Strains Using the MEGA-11 Software

Figure 4. Multiple Sequence Alignment Showing Nucleic Acid Differences between the Study *E. gingivalis* Isolates and the Global NCBI-BLAST *E. gingivalis* Isolates/Strains Using the NCBI-Viewer

Figure 5. Phylogenetic Tree Analysis of the Current Study *E. gingivalis* Isolates and Global NCBI-BLAST *E. gingivalis* Isolates / Strains

Sociodemographic Data

The findings of sociodemographic risk factors were shown a significant variation ($p < 0.05$) in values of their groups (Table 3). Concerning the health status of study population, the incidence rate of *E. gingivalis* infection was increased significantly ($p < 0.0334$; 95%CI: 52.21 to 68.62) in dental patients (12.96%) more than the healthy individuals (3.45%). In addition, the risk of infection (OR and RR) was elevated significantly ($p < 0.0001$) in dental patients (4.1702 and 3.4426, respectively) than those of healthy ones (0.2398 and 0.2905, respectively).

Significantly, the occurrence of *E. gingivalis* infection in individuals of 20-35 (11.91%) and 36-50 (12.12%) years was significantly higher ($p < 0.032$) than those of < 20 (6.25%) and > 50 (7.69%) years old. However, the risk of *E. gingivalis* infection (OR and RR) was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) in population of 36-50 years old (1.2611 and 1.2046, respectively) than those of 20-35 (1.1486 and 1.1170, respectively), > 50 (0.6548 and 0.7041, respectively) and < 20 (0.5095 and 0.5672, respectively) years old.

Regarding residence of study population, though no significant variation ($p < 0.0562$) was found in positive *E. gingivalis* infection between rural (8.82%), sub-urban (8.33%) and urban (12.09%), values of OR and RR revealed that individuals of urban areas were significantly ($p < 0.0001$) at higher risk of *E. gingivalis* infection (1.4438 and 1.3480, respectively) than those of rural (0.7339 and 0.7770, respectively) and sub-urban (0.7208 and 0.7637, respectively) areas.

The occurrence and risk (OR, RR) of *E. gingivalis* infection was significantly higher ($p < 0.05$) in smokers (20%, 3.5833 and 2.7222, respectively) than non-smokers (6.52%, 0.2791 and 0.3673, respectively).

For marital status, no significant difference ($p < 0.542$) was recorded between the married (11.63%) and non-married (9.8%) individuals; however, the risk (OR and RR) of *E. gingivalis* infection was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) in married (1.2105 and 1.1667, respectively) than non-married (0.8261 and 0.8571, respectively) individuals.

Relation to sex of study population, significant increases in *E. gingivalis* infection ($p < 0.0244$) was reported in females (12.87%) more than males (5.56%). Additionally, the risk of *E. gingivalis* infection was significantly higher ($p < 0.0001$) in females (2.5114 and 2.1667, respectively) than males (0.3982 and 0.4615, respectively).

According to pregnancy status, lack of significance ($p < 0.0619$) in incidence of *E. gingivalis* infection was observed between the pregnant (14.29%) and non-pregnant (12.64%) population; however, pregnant individuals were appeared significantly ($p < 0.0088$ and $p < 0.0068$) at higher risk of *E. gingivalis* infection (1.1515 and 1.1136, respectively) than non-pregnant ones (0.8684 and 0.8980, respectively).

Table 3. Association of Positive Infections to Sociodemographic Risk Factors

Factor	Total No.	Positive	OR	RR
Health status				
Healthy	29	1 (3.45%)	0.2398	0.2905
Patient	108	14 (12.96%) *	4.1702 ****	3.4426 ****
p-value		0.0334	0.0001	0.0001
95% CI		52.21 to 68.62	0.2277 to 27.18	0.1816 to 21.89
Age (Year)				
< 20	16	1 (6.25%)	0.5095	0.5672
20-35	42	5 (11.91%) *	1.1486	1.1170
36-50	66	8 (12.12%) *	1.2611 ****	1.2046 ****
> 50	13	1 (7.69%)	0.6548	0.7041
p-value		0.032	0.0001	0.0001
95% CI		4.762 to 14.22	0.3091 to 14.78	0.4044 to 1.392

Residence				
Rural	34	3 (8.82%)	0.7339	0.7770
Sub-urban	12	1 (8.33%)	0.7208	0.7637
Urban	91	11 (12.09%)	1.4438 ****	1.3480 ****
p-value		0.0562	0.0001	0.0001
95% CI		-4.669 to 14.82	0.06151 to 1.994	0.1343 to 17.92
Smoking				
Smoker	45	9 (20%) *	3.5833 ****	2.7222 ****
Non-smoker	92	6 (6.52%)	0.2791	0.3673
p-value		0.0299	0.0001	0.0001
95% CI		72.38 to 98.90	0.1906 to 22.92	0.1342 to 16.51
Marital status				
Married	86	10 (11.63%)	1.2105 ****	1.1667 ****
Non-married	51	5 (9.8%)	0.8261	0.8571
p-value		0.0542	0.0001	0.0001
95% CI		-0.9112 to 22.34	0.1424 to 13.46	0.9550 to 12.97
Sex				
Female	101	13 (12.87%) *	2.5114	2.1667
Male	36	2 (5.56%)	0.3982	0.4615
p-value		0.0424	0.0001 ****	0.0001 ****
95% CI		37.23 to 55.66	0.1197 to 14.88	0.9519 to 12.15
Pregnancy status				
Pregnant	14	2 (14.29%)	1.1515 ***	1.1136 **
Non-pregnant	87	11 (12.64%)	0.8684	0.8980
p-value		0.0619	0.0008	0.0068
95% CI		-2.982 to 23.95	0.7886 to 2.809	0.3639 to 2.376

Discussion

Molecular findings of the resent study revealed that the percentage of positive *E. gingivalis* infection in individuals of Wasit province (Iraq) was 10.95% that comparatively in agreement with the result of Abbass et al. (2020) in AL Muthanna (9.47%); but lowered than identified by other Iraqi researchers in Nineveh (71.79%) by the conventional and molecular assays (Al-Nuaimi et al., 2021), Salah El-Din (52%) by molecular assay (Al-Sarhan et al., 2021), Baghdad (46%) by molecular assay (Yassin et al., 2023), Maysan (36%) by molecular assay (Mushtaq and Al-Abboodi, 2024), Wasit (73%) using the microscopy (Naeem, 2024), and Thi-Qar (46.33%) using the microscopy (Shayal and ALAboody, 2025). Globally, the occurrence rate of *E. gingivalis* infection was 26.92% in Denmark by the molecular assay (Stensvold et al., 2011), 28.75% in Egypt using the microscopy (El-Dardiry and Shabaan, 2016), 81.37% in Poland using the microscopy (Luszczak et al., 2016), 73.53% in Mexico by the molecular assay (Garcia et al., 2018), 86.67% in France by molecular assay (Dubar et al., 2019), 22.5-40% in Nigeria by the microscopy (Adamu et al., 2020; Ani et al., 2020), 30.69% in Turkey by the microscopy (Arpağ and Kaya, 2020), and 67.47% in Germany by molecular technique (Bao et al., 2020). In a systemic review and meta-analysis study described the current global status and the epidemiology of *E. gingivalis* infection in human, the prevalence rate was at 37% (95% CI, 29-46%). In that order, Jordan (87% CI, 81-92) and Portugal (3% CI, 0-10) were found to have the highest and lowest pooled prevalence of *E. gingivalis* infection, respectively. The prevalence rate was the greatest in reference to the Americas (56% CI, 31-79%) with the commonest across all middle age groups 46-55 years [61% CI, 21-94]. The molecular methods and the direct methods had the highest pooled prevalence of 53% (95% CI, 24-81%), and 36% (95% CI, 25-47%), respectively (Badri et al., 2021). However, difference in occurrence of *E. gingivalis* infection in human in above mentioned studies might be attributed to variation in study design, methodology, variation in health status (patient and/or healthy) bias and errors in data collection and analysis, and the role of chance, especially with small sample size.

Phylogenetic analysis of study *E. gingivalis* isolates revealed their identities to the Japanese *E. gingivalis* isolates of human saliva source as well as to the Mexican *E. gingivalis* strains of human periodontal scraping source. Based on these data, various *E. gingivalis* isolates and/or strains circulate in Iraqi population with indicating to the role of phylogeny in discovering different pathogenic species and their strains in examined samples. Additionally, some studies proposed an association between *E. gingivalis* and periodontal diseases (Ibrahim and Abbas, 2012; Rafiei et al., 2017; Vlasa et al., 2024); while in other studies, it has shown that RNA levels of *E. gingivalis* was elevated and the microbial diversity was reduced in the inflamed areas of the mouth (Ebersole et al., 2021; Jiao et al., 2022; Keeler et al., 2023). Bao et al. (2021) indicated that *E. gingivalis* is able to invade lacerated oral mucosa, where it ingests fragments of live cells, suggesting pathogenous potential.

Our sociodemographic data revealed that the incidence rate of *E. gingivalis* infection was varied significantly throughout the factors of health status, age, smoking, and sex but not for other factors including residence, marital status, and pregnancy status. Subsequently, this study indicates that the incidence rate of *E. gingivalis* in dental patients more than healthy, in 36-50 years age old more than other age categories, smokers more than non-smokers, and in females more than males. In general, several studies have been demonstrated the existence of *E. gingivalis* in healthy population as well as patients with various oral and dental lesions (Ghabanchi et al., 2010; Al-Nuaimi et al., 2021; Yaseen et al., 2021). However, Bonner et al. (2014) reported that *E. gingivalis* play a potential link between colonization of gingival crevices and periodontitis. Badri et al. (2021) mentioned that *E. gingivalis* infection was associated with 4.34-fold increased risk of oral diseases. In Turkey, Örsten et al. (2023) detected the significant higher presence of *E. gingivalis* infection in patients with periodontal disease than in healthy individuals. Mushtaq and Al-Abboodi (2024) showed that the prevalence rate of *E. gingivalis* infection in orthodontic patients (47%) was higher than non-orthodontic participants with increasing the incidence rate of infection in males (70.8%) than females (39.4%) as well as in 10-20 years old (50%) of non-orthodontic participants more than other age groups [21-30 (16.9%), 31-40 (29.4%) and 41-50 (0%)] but throughout the age groups of 10-20 (55.9%) and 31-40 (58.3%) years old of orthodontic patients more than 21-30 years old (23.3%). Al-Nuaimi et al. (2021) found that the prevalence rate of *E. gingivalis* was higher in males (81.35%) than females (73.84%); whereas Naeem (2024) reported that *E. gingivalis* was significantly higher in females (59%) than males (41%) as well as in population aged 21-30 years old (54.55%) more than those of >10 (4.55%), 11-20 (18.18%), 31-40 (13.64%), 41-50 (9.09%), and 51-60 (0%) years old. The increasing risk of *E. gingivalis* infection in smokers has been confirmed by many researchers nationally and internationally (Ghabanchi et al., 2010; Hassan et al., 2019; Badri et al., 2021; Fadhil et al., 2022). This might be related to that smoking increase the risk of gingivitis and periodontal disease, and can create a more favorable environment for this parasite by altering oral saliva components and decreasing the availability of oxygen.

Conclusion

This study indicate the marked incidence of *E. gingivalis* in population of Wasit province (Iraq), with significant association between positivity and various sociodemographic risk factors in particular health status, age, smoking, and sex. In addition, sequencing data and phylogenetic analysis of study *E. gingivalis* isolates demonstrated their close-relationships to global NCBI-BLAST Japanese isolate and Mexican strain. Therefore, this study suggesting that the sequencing and phylogenetic analysis of *E. gingivalis* targeting the *S rRNA* gene can provide a high-resolution taxonomic profiling that is especially cost-effect and efficient for samples with low pathogenic biomass, making it a valuable complement to genomic approaches. Also, recognizing this cyclical behavior informs the optimal timing of anti-protozoal interventions, which could be refined through monitoring of salivary biomarkers linked to trophozoite activity.

Conflict of Interest

No.

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